

SCHOOL CLIMATE AND JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The study is examined that the school climate and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Tirunelveli District relation to the background variables. A self-made scale was used to measure the school climate of 153 secondary school teachers from Tirunelveli District, Tamil Nadu. Simple random sampling method was adopted for analyzing the data. The testing of hypotheses using appropriate statistical techniques revealed that there is significant difference between rural and urban school secondary teachers in their school climate and the comparison of their mean scores reveal that the urban school teachers are better than rural school teachers; There is significant difference between rural and urban school secondary teachers in their Job Satisfaction and the comparison of their mean scores reveal that the urban school teachers are found to be better than the rural school teachers; There is significant relationship between school climate and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Key Words: School Climate, Job Satisfaction & Secondary Teachers

Introduction:

According to the *World Book Encyclopaedia* (1988) education is the process by which people acquire knowledge, skills, habits, values and attitudes. Education is the process through which develops the human personality. Sarvapalli Radhakrishnan (1951) said "the three things vital dynamism, intellectual efficiency and spiritual direction together constitute the proper aim of education". According to Redden (1984), "Education is the deliberate and systematic influence extended by the mature person upon the immature through instruction and discipline for harmonious development of physical, aesthetic, social and spiritual powers on human being". The teacher must work for drawing out the best from the child-body, mind and spirit. The end of all knowledge must be building up of character and personality. The sole aim of education is encouraging virtues and discouraging vices. The education not only prepares the child for education but also shapes him into a useful citizen of the society. Education teach us the truths, charity, righteousness, honesty, sacrifice, tolerance, punctuality, loyalty and faithfulness are also virtues which should be inculcated in the young generation. Mahatma Gandhi emphatically stresses about truth is the ultimate aim of education.

Significance of the Study:

The school climate refers to the environment which constructs a better learning and teaching. The teacher is influenced by the environment and school climate for the better teaching. The school climate supports the teacher and promote in teaching learning process. The facilities available in the school, the nature of school, the individual differences among the students, the non-supportive learning environment at home or of parents, the affecting socio-economic factors are not considered when a student's academic achievement becomes low or poor (Anandharaja, Balakrishnan & Lawrence, 2016). The high technology and well developed school climate help the teachers and students to use the better class room in teaching learning. The teacher with high esteem and self-confident can create a better learning place for the students. These teachers are risk takers and say yes to new idea or skills because old controlling styles and restriction are the qualities of inefficient teachers. It is likely that the job satisfaction accompanies a sense of school climate and to contribute to attain the best result. Today teachers are expected to nurture their students in addition to values, high level intellectual skills and ability to learn independently. Teachers are responsible for guiding the students to learn by providing clear directions and explanations in order to educate the future generation (Rani & Deepa, 2017). A committed teacher develops knowledge, desirable attitudes and required skills (Jane & Kumar, 2017). The teachers have to perform different roles effectively so that they must be satisfied with the job. Otherwise, decline in job satisfaction may lead to alienation, apathy, absenteeism, neglect of work and giving up the job and poor peer adjustment. Hence the investigator selected the topic school climate and job satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of school climate of secondary school teachers.
- ✓ To find out the level of job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Null Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers in their school climate.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the School Climate and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers.

Methodology: The researcher has used to the survey method for obtaining the data.

Sample for the Study: The investigator has randomly selected 153 secondary school teachers from Tirunelveli districts.

Tool Used: The researcher has used the standardized scale for job satisfaction by Amalraj and Lalithambika Devi (1999) and school climate scale developed and validated by the investigator and guide.

Statistical Techniques Used: Percentage analysis, Arithmetic mean, Standard deviation, 't' test, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation were used for analysis of the data.

Table 1: Level of School Climate of Secondary School Teachers with regard to Total Sample

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
School Climate	23	14.1	103	63.6	27	22.2

It is inferred from the above table shows that 14.1% of teachers have low level, 63.6% of moderate level and 22.2% of teachers have high level of school climate.

Table 2: Level of Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers with regard to Total Sample

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
School Climate	17	11.1	120	78.4	16	10.5

It is inferred from the above table shows that 11.1% of secondary school teachers have low level, 78.4% of moderate level and 10.5% of high level of job satisfaction.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers in their school climate.

Table 3: Difference between Rural and Urban Secondary School Teachers in their School Climate

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remark
Locality of Institution	Rural	120	140.77	14.084	3.279	S
	Urban	33	150.67	15.696		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table shows that there is a significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers in their school climate. While comparing the mean value of rural (M=140.77) and urban (M=150.67) school teachers in their school climate. Urban school teachers are better than rural school teachers.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction

Table 4: Difference between Rural and Urban Secondary School Teachers in their Job Satisfaction

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Locality of Institution	Rural	120	99.78	9.924	4.020	S
	Urban	33	108.27	10.972		

(At 5% level of significance the Table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table shows that and there is significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction. While comparing the mean value of rural (M=99.78) and urban (M=108.27) school teachers in their school climate. Urban school teachers are better than rural school teachers.

Null Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the School Climate and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers.

Table 3: Relationship between School Climate and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

ΣX	ΣY	ΣX^2	ΣY^2	ΣXY	Correlation	N	γ Value	Table Value	Remark
21864	15546	3158434	1597036	2234005	0.511	153	0.511	0.117	S

It is inferred from the above table shows that there is significant relationship between School Climate and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers.

Findings:

- ✓ 22.2% of secondary school teachers have high level of school climate.
- ✓ 10.5% of secondary school teachers have high level of Job Satisfaction.
- ✓ Significant difference exists between rural and urban school secondary teachers in their school climate. While comparing mean score of rural and urban school secondary school teachers, Urban(Mean=150.67) school teachers better than rural(Mean=140.77) school teachers in their school climate.
- ✓ Significant difference exists between Rural and Urban school secondary teachers in their Job Satisfaction, While comparing mean score of rural and urban school secondary school teachers, Urban(Mean=108.27) school teachers better than rural(Mean=99.78) school teachers in their job satisfaction.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between School Climate and Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers.

Implications:

- ✓ To create a healthy climate Self-awareness program should be arranged for teachers.
- ✓ There should be a cordial relationship between teachers and the head of the institution.
- ✓ The teachers at secondary level should also be given one or two leisure periods keeping in mind of their work load.
- ✓ The head of the institution should provide the opportunity for suitable working space, facilities to achieve one's status and prestige in job etc.
- ✓ Since school climate and job satisfaction of teachers are interrelated, proper care should be given by the management to have a healthy job satisfaction.

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